

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FORMATION OF MOTIVATION TO PRESERVE HEALTH IN
CHILDREN, ADOLESCENTS AND YOUTH IN MODERN
EDUCATIONAL SPACE**¹Ekaterina Y. Domrachyova, ¹Oksana Y. Ilyakhina, ¹Larisa A. Kadutskaya,
¹Sergey S. Klimenko

Belgorod State University, 308015 85, Pobedy Str., Belgorod, Russia.

Katya260688@mail.ru

²Igor N. OzerovBelgorod Law Institute of Ministry of the Internal
of the Russian Federation named after I.D. Putilin

308024 71, Gorkogo Str., Belgorod, Russia

Katya260688@mail.ru

Article Received: March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

The reason for the majority of diseases in our time is the sedentary lifestyle of a teenager who was not instilled with such a useful habit as sport in early childhood. After all, if we take into account the full usefulness of physical exercises, you can avoid a huge number of diseases that a person develops from early childhood.

A healthy lifestyle has always been the basis of longevity and prosperity of citizens. However, today many people prefer to connect their lives with sports, while misinterpreting the concept of a "healthy lifestyle".

Health is the highest value for a person, it is the basis of everything, thanks to which a person builds his life path and confidently overcomes obstacles. That is why health must be protected from a young age. In early childhood, his parents monitor the health of the child, during the school period, the child is already a little detached from mom and dad, and he will have to pay attention to his own health. But not all children tend to play sports, eat vitamins, temper, and also take other actions to maintain their health. That is why it is necessary to somehow motivate children, adolescents, and students to maintain their health and instill in them the values of a healthy lifestyle.

Keywords: *physical exercises, physical education, sports, teenager, health, sports skills, strength training, cardio training, curvature of the spine, obesity, martial arts, popular sports.*

Corresponding author:**Ekaterina Y. Domrachyova,**

Belgorod State University, 308015 85, Pobedy Str.,

Belgorod, Russia.

Katya260688@mail.ru

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ekaterina Y. Domrachyova et al, **Formation Of Motivation To Preserve Health In Children, Adolescents And Youth In Modern Educational Space.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(05).

INTRODUCTION:

The unified concept of “healthy lifestyle” does not exist in the scientific literature. So, according to scientists in this field, a healthy lifestyle is a joint activity of a person and society aimed at maintaining and strengthening health. A number of authors believe that a healthy lifestyle is a combination of personal and social practices for maintaining or achieving health, based on interest in health, its value perception and goal-setting, stimulating its implementation in everyday life.

Younger school age is a kind of foundation, because about 35% of physiological and mental illnesses of adults are laid in childhood, therefore, instilling in a child the values of a healthy lifestyle is a very responsible stage.

It would seem, where can a child have mental illness? But, as you know, in recent years, the volume of workloads has increased in schools, the intensity and emotional stress of the educational process has increased sharply, and children are increasingly being hospitalized with nervous breakdowns. It also affects the functional state of the cardiovascular system. In addition, due to the large volume of the school curriculum, there is a strong tension in the visual apparatus, as a result of which pupils' vision is impaired.

RESEARCH METHODS:

While in class, a schoolchild or student should monitor their posture. Indeed, due to the incorrectly selected posture, the student's spine is subjected to deformation. And what can we say about the diet ... Children, as a rule, do not observe it. This is a dry food, large breaks between meals, fasting, eating instant food with hot spices, sauces, mayonnaise, smoked, canned foods, fried foods. Basically, children do not choose healthy, but tasty food, so they have a snack with sandwiches, chips, crackers, soda, which contains dyes that are harmful to health. In this regard, the pathology of the digestive system is formed in children. These can be diseases such as gastritis, gastroduodenitis, dyspepsia, pancreatitis and others.

The intensification of the educational process also affects the violation of the regime of the day and rest of schoolchildren, which negatively affects the physical and mental health of children. What can cause health problems? Of course, to limit life and social functions. Subsequently, all this is fraught with a decrease in physical activity, mobility, the ability to engage in ordinary activities, the ability to get a decent education. Indeed, it is health, as the main asset of man, that helps him to make his existence on earth worthy and productive. And in order to provide children with a bright and healthy

environment, we must create a healthy environment for them in the educational space.

What does it mean to be healthy for a child? This means developing your physical and spiritual strengths in harmony, possessing stamina and balance, being able to withstand the action of both adverse environmental factors and your inner world, i.e. live a healthy life. According to the World Health Organization, the health of each person by 50-54% depends on his lifestyle. Another 18-20% - from environmental conditions, 20-22% - from a hereditary predisposition to diseases and only 8-10% - from the level of development of medical care.

The healthy lifestyle of the young generation is the key to the well-being of the nation as a whole. That is why it is necessary to form motivation in children to maintain a healthy lifestyle.

In our opinion, motivation should be formed through project activities. What does this term mean? Project activity is one of the most productive educational technologies. It requires the child's cognitive activity and the ability to use the existing knowledge of the student. In the process of implementing the project, the child is faced with the need to manifest his independence, looking for a compromise, coordinating his goal with other children. In joint activities, collective experiences bring children together with each other and with adults; contribute to the improvement of the microclimate in the group; Develop creative abilities of children; helps to form the core competencies of the pupils.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY:

How to maintain health? How to convince children that health should be protected from an early age? How to develop this habit in them - to observe a healthy lifestyle?

It is known that mastering knowledge is faster if the child is an active participant in what is happening. Therefore, in my opinion, one should conduct various conversations with children, which would be filled with game plots, characters. It is necessary to select the appropriate didactic and demonstration material, including mock-ups, we alternate different types of activity. All this would lure children, and work would progress more efficiently.

To eradicate the prosperity of bad habits in adolescence, you should create a project “Let's say no!” bad habits. " Carrying out work in this direction, it is important to remember that the game is an important factor in understanding the world around us. We cannot always achieve the desired result by explaining to a child or teenager “what is good and what is bad”.

But with the help of staging games that contribute to the emotional empathy of the heroes, we have more chances to learn how to act and act in accordance with moral requirements. Teenagers with enthusiasm take part in the work on the presentation, learn to speak to the audience, answer unplanned questions. The results of such work can be the release of posters, drawings, booklets in which children and adolescents express their attitude to bad habits.

Also, in our opinion, a lot depends on the personnel who are engaged in educational and pedagogical work. Therefore, teachers should undertake activities to promote a healthy lifestyle among their students. And for this you need to spend days of health. After all, this form of work allows you to form the need for a useful leisure activity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

As you know, most children are virtual. They spend all their free time at computers. In the modern world, communication is losing its essence live, mostly children communicate via the Internet. Because of this, adolescents spoil their eyesight, curvature of the spine occurs, and more simply, thinking ceases to work, the computer thinks for the child. A project activity helps children and adolescents to rationally organize their leisure time. After all, if a person from childhood is able to plan his day, then in the future it will be easier and easier for him to raise his children.

Thus, project activity is the most effective way of creating motivation to maintain health in children, adolescents and youth.

As for youth, here each person already monitors his health and decides whether he should observe a healthy lifestyle or not. Each one sets his own value guidelines, so at this age it is difficult to influence a person and impose certain opinions on him. But still worth a try.

Of course, parenting forms the character of a person and affects his future life. Therefore, parents should, from a very early age, have their child instilled in him sports, proper nutrition, taught him to dress according to the weather, tempered, in general, to maintain a healthy lifestyle. But these actions are not unique to parents. In all educational organizations, curators, teachers or superiors seek to motivate their students to maintain a healthy lifestyle.

Speaking to our institute, here students from the very moment they enter the institute temper both themselves and their character. Playing sports for our students is the basis of successful service. Several times a week we have physical training classes in which we develop our physical qualities,

such as dexterity, speed, flexibility, improve fighting techniques, and overcome various obstacles. All this tempers students, makes them stronger and more resistant to various external influences. Also, sports institutes are regularly held at our institute, in which students compete with each other, developing self-determination, willpower, perseverance and discipline.

It has been repeatedly proved by many researchers and professors in the field of physical education that physical activity not only positively affects the formation of the teenage body, but also allows it to heal the child with the help of physical activity.

Physical culture is one of the components of the general social culture, which allows a person to develop intellectually and physically, to strengthen and maintain health, through physical activity.

Constant movement and exercise affect the development of the child, as well as the growth that occurs without various diseases or without the development of pathologies.

Playing sports not only helps to acquire certain sports skills in various sports, but also helps to be much more stable in stressful situations and to perceive the environment and negative reality positively.

Children who are familiar with sports from a young age are much more confident in the team than those who do nothing. The big plus is that it can affect the choice of a future profession. A teenager who has had an interesting occupation since childhood, whether it be wrestling, boxing or sambo, will already plan to connect his future life with this sport, which will affect him only positively.

With a sedentary lifestyle, a teenager will acquire health problems, bad habits as a result of which he will become irritable, uncommunicative, and completely cease to enjoy life and see it in all its glory.

Health is the state of an organism in which it feels satisfied physically, spiritually and socially. A person in good health is capable of many tests of his endurance, endurance. He is also constantly in a cheerful state of mind, seems contented and cheerful.

If you regularly perform physical exercises, then you can increase muscle tone, which will positively affect the appearance, eliminate many diseases and increase the performance of the heart.

Physical exercises are elementary motor actions that are aimed at the physical development of a person.

There are various types of exercise:

- strength exercises (aimed at increasing muscle mass)

There are a huge number of these exercises, which are classified by muscle groups:

1. Exercises for back development
 2. Hip Muscle Exercise
 3. Exercises for the development of calf muscles
 4. Exercises for the development of the shoulder girdle
 5. Exercises for the development of the forearm
 6. Exercises for the development of pectoral muscles
- Etc.

There is also a classification of exercises on:

- basic (several joints are involved)
- insulating (one joint is involved)

The following type of exercise is:

-cardio exercises (aimed at increasing endurance, reducing body fat)

1. Running
2. Cycling
3. Walking long distances
4. Swimming

And the third kind of exercise is:

- muscle stretching exercises (aimed at improving the flexibility of the body)

1. Yoga
2. Pilates
3. Fitness

Exercise affects not only all muscle groups, but also on joints, ligaments, which, during exercise, become strong, elastic and strong, which helps to increase muscle mass.

In the 21st century, much attention has been paid to such a relatively new trend as "anorexia." Anorexia is a disease that is accompanied by a complete lack of appetite and a disorder of the whole body.

Young girls, leading a healthy lifestyle, proper nutrition and daily training, destroy themselves and their body primarily, without realizing it. Scientists in the field of anorexia medicine devoted a large number of works, because, today, a large number of girls die, falling into the network of this disease. First of all, this is due to the fact that fighting for a beautiful body and the pursuit of popularity on social networks, people forget about health.

If a person is inactive, then his muscles deteriorate, become flabby, lose their tone, their elasticity and strength decrease. Such a lifestyle in which movement is at a minimum lead to various diseases, pathological changes in the body.

Strength training, it is possible to improve posture, as they are aimed at increasing muscle mass, and, therefore, to strengthen the muscles (especially the muscles of the body). If you choose the right special exercises, then it is possible to avoid such a problem as curvature of the spine. Often the cause of this disease is obesity, which occurs in adolescents from a sedentary lifestyle. Correctly selected exercises and specialist advice can be achieved without particular difficulty in solving this problem.

Inoculating daily correctly performed physical exercises for children and adolescents, you can notice a one-year increase in body length, mass, circumference and chest excursion, as well as lung capacity and muscle strength.

In addition to strength training, there are various sports * martial arts, soccer, hockey, volleyball, karate, which also positively affect the younger generation. If we are talking about a lesson, about a specific form, then, having analyzed the psyche of a teenager, we can say that as a result of playing football, he becomes much more confident in his abilities, improves himself not only physically, but also socially.

Exercise not only helps to improve well-being and health, but also temper the character so that he is fully prepared to cope with various tests. All this can be explained by the fact that those sports that are in physical activity are significantly traumatic and when choosing a sport of interest, you need to be prepared for the fact that you will have to endure pain and cope with it, thereby overstepping your emotions.

One of the most relevant in our time is boxing. This sport not only tempers health, but also spirit! If you want your child to be self-confident, have firmness, composure and easily cope with all problems both morally and physically, then your choice should definitely fall on the side of boxing. In addition to these advantages, this sport has others, for example, it develops honesty, and adequacy which are the most important moral qualities of a person. If we generalize power sports, we can immediately conclude that this is patience and definitely harmony with oneself.

Based on all of the above, it can be concluded that it is better to choose an active and healthy lifestyle in childhood, while laying down the right habits for a growing organism, setting a goal and motivating success in the activity that he chose to engage in.

Such simple tips and actions that you can add to a habit that do not take up more time should be performed daily in order to avoid negative consequences associated with health.

1. Carrying out morning exercises or walking.

2. Carrying out a physical pause between training sessions.
3. Stay in the air for at least 3.5 hours per day.
4. 5-6 meals a day, fortification, twice a year (November-December, January-February), general UV irradiation according to the accelerated method with additional intake of ascorbic acid.
5. Hardening procedures (wiping, bath, dousing with cold water).

The main thing in life is that all people are healthy. And what is needed for this? To begin with, you should follow a number of simple rules on which success is based. Parents need to properly educate their children, and children need to listen to their parents and take note of all their advice, as well as try to monitor their own health and not commit rash acts. And if every person makes every effort to maintain a healthy lifestyle, there will be a healthy nation in our world.

CONCLUSION:

In our opinion, in order to start practicing, monitor your health and adhere to a healthy lifestyle, you do not need to deplete your body with diets and various diets that contain substances that negatively affect human health in general. First of all, an important criterion for a healthy lifestyle is a proper balanced diet, which will be aimed at enriching the body with vitamins. For this, you do not need to use chemical additives that will adversely affect the human body and the brain in the first place. It is enough to revise your diet and make changes in the form of adding various foods with a predominance of vitamins A and B. Also, physical training is an integral part of normal human life.

A healthy lifestyle contributes to:

- first, increase the body's resistance to the effects of adverse environmental factors;
- secondly, the education of mental stability and moral-volitional qualities;
- thirdly, the formation of readiness to carry extreme physical and mental stress.

Also, a lot of important factor affecting human health is exercise. You need to start your morning daily with a five-minute charge, which will help awaken the body and tune the muscles of the body to work all day. At the same time, it's not necessary to go to the fitness room and devote two or more hours to training, just pay more attention to your body also in the form of walks in the fresh air, swimming in the pool, which puts stress on all muscle groups.